

Adsorption of Fulvic Acid (FA) on Benzene/Water Interface

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It has been found that fulvic acid (FA) extracted from soil can be used to stabilize the oil droplets dispersed in water. The present investigation has been carried out to determine the adsorbed amount of FA per ml. of benzene dispersed and the data obtained have been applied to test the applicability of different adsorption isotherms proposed for the adsorption of unionised solutes at the oil/water interface.

Works on unionised solutes such as butyric, lauric, palmitic and stearic acids at oil/water interface have been reported^{1,2}. We have selected FA as the stabilizer since practically very little work has been done on the adsorption of FA at oil/water interface.

EXPERIMENTAL

FA isolated from Palampur soil has been selected. The humus from the surface layers of the sample was extracted with 0.5 N Na₂CO₃ and the fulvic acid was obtained by the usual procedure³ from this extract. FA was then converted into its barium salt, a form in which it was relatively more stable³. FA was prepared before use by passing the barium fulvate suspension through a column of resin, Amberlite IR-120 in the H-form. The elemental composition of FA was found to be C, 47.60%, H, 4.38% and N, 3.02%.

Measurement of total adsorption on the emulsion globules : All the emulsions have been prepared by the same method as used by Kundu and Ghosh⁴ keeping the oil/water ratio for each of the emulsion constant. These emulsions have then been passed through a hand operated homogenizer. All the emulsions have been allowed to stand till the aqueous phase has become clear. The concentration of FA in gm per ml. in the aqueous phase has been determined by usual conductometric titration with previously standardised NaOH. From the difference in concentration of FA in the aqueous phase before and after emulsification the amount adsorbed on per ml. of benzene dispersed has been estimated. This investigation has been carried out in absence and in presence of a neutral electrolyte such as NaCl freed from surfactants by heating.

The room temperature was $28 \pm 1^\circ$ and oil/water was 10/100.

1. W. D. Harkins and H. H. King, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 970.
2. A. F. H. Ward and L. Tordai, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1952, **71**, 482.
3. C. Datta and S. K. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 555.
4. L. Kundu and B. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 39.

DISCUSSION

The applicability of Freundlich⁵ and Langmuir⁶ isotherms to the adsorption of FA on benzene/water interface has been tested with the data obtained. A plot of $\log n$ against $\log C$ yields a straight line [Fig. I(b)] for the ionic strength 0.01. Deviation from linearity in

Fig. 1.
Concentration expressed in gm/ml

the absence of salt is observed in the low concentration region. Therefore, it may be concluded that Freundlich isotherm holds for the adsorption of FA in presence of neutral electrolyte on this interface over the range of concentration of FA investigated. The actual isotherm of Freundlich type which holds well is $n = k.C^{1/3}$ in presence of salt and $n = k.C^{2/3}$ in the absence of salt only over the moderate range of concentrations. According to Davies⁷ if an excess of 1-1 salt is present in the water ($C_{salt} \approx C_i$ and $C_i \gg C$) an approximate isotherm for adsorption at the oil/water interface of the type $n = 5.35 \times 10^{13} \times C^{1/3} \times C_i^{1/3}$

$\exp \left\{ \frac{810 m}{RT} \right\}$ at 50° , holds well and this approximate isotherm is again true only when ψ_0

> 100 mv and is identical with the isotherm $n = k.C^{1/3}$, C being the concentration of the long chain ions and C_i , the total ionic strength. At fixed values of C_i and m rectilinear plots of n against $C^{1/3}$ has been predicted and verified experimentally for the adsorption of long chain sulphates at oil/water interface as reported by Davies⁷. For the system investigated by us this predicted approximate isotherm holds well in presence of salt. The isotherm predicted by Davies⁸ $n = 5.35 \times 10^{13} \times C^{2/3} \exp \left\{ \frac{810 m}{RT} \right\}$ at 50° , (when $C_i = C$, since no salt is

added) = $k.C^{2/3}$ also holds over the moderate range of concentrations in absence of salt.

The complete equation of Langmuir⁶ for unionised solutes is

$$n = \frac{\beta \frac{C}{\alpha}}{\left(1 + \frac{C}{\alpha}\right)} \quad \dots (1)$$

5. H. Freundlich, Colloid and Capillary Chemistry, Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1926.

6. I. Langmuir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1848.

7. J. T. Davies, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1958, **A-245**, 417.

where $\beta = n_0$ and $\alpha = n_0 \left(\frac{B_2}{B_1} \right) \exp \left(\frac{W}{-RT} \right)$, the terms having usual significance and it holds

well for the adsorption of unionised butyric acid at the benzene/water interface. According to the equation (1), a plot of $1/n$ against $1/C$ should be linear. For the system investigated by us deviation from linearity is observed only in the low concentration region [Fig. II(a,b)] both in presence and in absence of salt. This deviation is due to less adsorption than that expected from equation (1) [Fig. III] putting $\alpha = 0.8771 \times 10^{-3}$ and $\beta = 5.263 \times 10^{-3}$ in

Fig. II.

Fig. III

presence of salt and $\alpha = 3.646 \times 10^{-3}$ and $\beta = 8.333 \times 10^{-3}$ in absence of salt in the equation (1), the values of α and β being calculated from the plot of $1/n$ vs $1/C$.

The less adsorption of FA may be due to diffusion of the FA molecules in the bulk phase from a higher concentration immediately below the interface as observed with the film of lauric acid^{8,9}. Since the concentration in the bulk is very low diffusion may be assumed

8. F. Sebba and H. V. A. Briscoe, *Jour. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 114.

9. C. C. Addison and S. K. Hutchinson, *ibid.*, 1949, 3395.

to occur by convection from the higher concentration layer just below the interface to the bulk and thus from the interface the FA molecules desorb into the underlying aqueous phase leading to less adsorption.

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